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INTERNATIONALISATION AND INTERCULTURALISM IN THREE EUROPEAN CONTEXTS: A BRIEF REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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Abstract. This paper explores literature on internationalisation and interculturalism in higher education in Ireland, Romania, and France. It identifies shared themes and national differences shaped by political, historical, and linguistic factors. Internationalisation is a major policy goal across all three countries, often linked to economic and institutional priorities and with English increasingly used as a medium of instruction. However, intercultural skills remain underdeveloped, with limited integration into curricula and student life, thus creating a gap between policy-level commitments and meaningful intercultural practice. While national strategies vary, all three contexts face common challenges in balancing global aspirations with local identities. Therefore, arguments exist for more inclusive and more reflective approaches to internationalisation, beyond the instrumental ones. Future research should examine more deeply how institutional culture, power dynamics, and language policy affect students' experiences and intercultural global education.

Keywords: language policy; European Higher Education; globalisation; reform; English as medium of instruction.

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1. Introduction

This review of literature aims to give a brief overview of research published on internationalisation and interculturalism in higher education in three European contexts: Ireland, Romania, and France, as part of an INGENIUM-funded research group (<https://ingenium-university.eu/>). Undertaking a review of published research, interrogating both the theoretical and practical synergies between interculturalism and internationalisation in each of the Higher Education (HE) contexts is viewed as a critical first step in understanding the current state of knowledge on internationalisation in different European contexts, in order to identify any gaps in existing studies and help refine research questions for further study. The review outlines the research country by country and thematic commonalities are discussed briefly in the conclusion.

2. Romania

2.1. The Context of the Research

Published in the past eleven years in either anthologies by reputable publishers (the volume edited by Grosu-Rădulescu and the two volumes edited by Curaj *et al.* for Springer) or academic journals (in Romania, Turkey, Poland), the reviewed articles cover the topics of internationalisation, intercultural education, and communication, as well as English language teaching in the context of an increasingly globalised higher education.

2.2. English as a Means of Europeanisation and Globalisation

All reviewed materials demonstrate an interest, on the part of Romanian foreign language instructors, in teaching practices that are adapted to the needs of the modern world, emphasising the role of languages (especially English as the acknowledged *lingua franca*) as a means of Europeanisation and globalisation. This promotes internationalisation in two directions: outgoing Romanian students and staff, whose proficiency in foreign languages (B1-B2 levels) allows them to visit or study at – mostly – Western universities, and incoming foreign students and staff who, in addition to requiring foreign languages skills themselves, expect the host institution to be international thus providing easy communication and teaching in foreign languages, notably English. While the poignancy of East-West study mobilities is explained historically by Grosu-Rădulescu (2018) through Romania's political and cultural isolation during communism, establishing a similarly strong West-East direction post-communism is a desirable objective for well-rounded

internationalisation, further spurring efforts on the part of Romanian institutions to enhance foreign language skills.

A second key point made in Grosu-Rădulescu's anthology concerns the interconnectedness between national cultures and their systems of education and foreign language acquisition, as skills taught in other subjects might impact learners' results in international English certification exams. A case in point is that of IELTS, where students from countries with low visual literacy (such as Romania) earn lower scores in the written part of the exam, where they need to interpret data from graphs and charts. While foreign language skills are the main vessel for internationalisation, the effectiveness of a country's education system as a whole cannot be ignored.

2.3. Internationalisation in Higher Education in Romania

Internationalisation in the five important Romanian universities comprising the *Universitaria* consortium is statistically analysed by Dima *et al.* (2023), who acknowledge the role of international relations offices in implementing Erasmus agreements for incoming and outgoing teachers and staff. Their analysis, based on data from official websites, of joint degrees, language centres, libraries, international conference organisation and programmes taught in foreign languages (mostly English, but also French, German, and Hungarian) provides a comprehensive overview of the internationalisation efforts of the five main Romanian institutions. One of the study weaknesses concerns the lack of information on challenges or feedback from students and staff on the success of mobilities from the point of view of interculturality. For this reason, its results should be correlated with the findings of Gheorghiu (2017) and Hamburg (2014), who record low levels of intercultural competence despite student exposure to mobilities and international events.

Deca *et al.* (2015) and Fiț *et al.* (2022) present an analysis of internationalisation of HEIs, with Fiț *et al.*'s study providing comparative analyses with Deca *et al.*'s results – deemed one of the first prominent review studies of internationalisation in third-level education in Romania. While internationalising the sector is one of the strongest priorities of post-communist Romania, a recurrent identified theme concerns the gap between intentions and actual outcomes in many universities and the system as a whole. One of the causes is ironically the institutional autonomy established after the 1990s, which, despite being an excellent starting point for encouraging initiatives and dynamic behaviour, can also result in a lack of strategic organisation at a national level and an opportunity for the weak segments of the sector to stagnate. The 2015 study states that internationalisation in Romanian universities was mainly focused on mobilities and partnerships while leaving aside or failing to recognise the importance of other dimensions of

internationalisation. On the other hand, regarding international cooperation, the general focus was on quantity at the expense of strategic and educational quality. Furthermore, institutional behaviour tended to be “reactive to immediate opportunities”. The year of publication is of significance, as in 2015 HEIs did not as yet benefit from the support of a series of strategic tools and experience, currently enjoyed in the field of internationalisation. Fiț *et al.* (2022), who principally focus on educational marketing for internationalisation purposes, highlight improvements in the sector over the seven-year period elapsed between the two articles. Initiatives at a national level (such as ‘Study in Romania’ through the National Council of Rectors, the Institutional Development funds through the National Council for Higher Education Financing) substantially improved overall local strategic perspectives, rendering Romanian HEIs considerably more attractive to the international market. Finally, in third-level education, weaknesses were observed in relation to the use of international languages in communication.

Conclusions regarding interculturality, internationalisation, and ESP in Romanian universities suggest a current incongruity between the apparently developing internationalisation in Romanian higher education and limited intercultural competence. The literature reviewed seems to indicate that acquisition of intercultural communication skills, key to fostering the education of European and global citizens, is hampered by the outdated legacy of the Romanian education system, where teaching of younger pupils, such as on how Turks and Hungarians are enemies, filter into higher education (Gheorghiu, 2017). The endeavours of FL teachers in implementing modern methodologies to enhance the objectives of internationalisation and intercultural competence is thus counteracted by the persistence of such mono-cultural mentalities. This is particularly concerning given the observation that “Romania may be considered among the fastest ‘learners’ as far as adaptation to new linguistic challenges is concerned”, which “might be a consequence of the country’s eagerness after the 1989 Revolution to come back to a cultural status similar to the one it had before the communist regime” (Grosu-Rădulescu, 2018, p. 5).

3. Ireland

3.1. The Context

The process of neoliberal marketisation of the Irish Higher Education sector is unambiguously reflected in recent national HE policy, which has underscored the instrumentalisation of the sector as a driver of the knowledge economy. To date, this paradigm has been most forcefully captured in 2011’s *National Strategy for Higher Education to 2030* (Department of Education and Skills, 2011), henceforth the Hunt Report. Of the imperative to foster entrepreneurialism among HE learners, the report notes that “[t]he sustainability

of the Irish economy relies on our success in nurturing indigenous enterprise as well as our ability to remain an attractive destination for leading multinational companies” (Department of Education and Skills, 2011, p. 37). The imperative for HE to underpin continued Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) from multinational companies is clearly set out here, and is reflective of Loxley’s (2014, p. 57) assertion that “[k]nowledge, whether codified or embodied, has taken on the status of becoming like land, capital and labour – a factor of production”. Of the urgency of maintaining the competitiveness of Irish HE on the global education market, the Hunt Report states that Ireland’s inherent advantage in having an English-speaking education is also being diminished by the global rise in English as a medium of education. As high-quality opportunities become available to students in their own countries and regions, they are increasingly deciding to study closer to home (Department of Education and Skills, 2011, p. 82).

Most recent research publications pertain to intercultural communication in the field of healthcare in Irish Higher Education. Among those relevant to MFL recent publications have focused on peer learning groups and tandems (Jeanneau and O’Riordan, 2015; Bruen and Sudhershan, 2015), utilising student linguistic super-diversity for the purposes of enhanced second language acquisition, intercultural awareness and intercultural communication (Nunan, 2017; Bruen and Kelly, 2016), government policy and strategy to support integration and interculturalism (Ni Chonail, 2018), and in one case investigating the potential of interlingual subtitling tasks to foster intercultural awareness (Borghetti and Lertola, 2014).

This section reviews studies that can be categorised as follows: a monolingual English bias and internationalisation in higher education.

3.2. A Monolingual English Bias in the Organisation and Outlook of Irish Higher Education

Pauwels (2014) is referenced extensively by Nunan (2017) and Bruen and Kelly (2016) and an associated concern in much of the scholarship in this review is that MFL is neglected in HE, in terms of its applications for fostering interculturalism, intercultural communication, improved social equality and more. Nunan’s research (2017) surveyed students who participated in an Irish University Wide Language Programme (UWLP) and observes a disconnect between their lived experiences and interests, and the general lack of value placed on language learning in HE despite the close link between language, thought, understanding, communication and culture. Nunan, therefore, links monolingual English-speaking models of HE in Ireland with failures to capitalise on the opportunities of growing linguistic and cultural diversity.

Bruen and Sudhershan (2015) also highlight pitfalls of the adoption of English as a *lingua franca* in HE, especially in popular fields such as

international business programmes. Research and scholarship in this area have tended to neglect the role of foreign language teaching and learning on many of these (international business) programmes, particularly for those based in Anglophone countries (Brannen *et al.*, 2014).

Ni Chonail's (2018) review of Irish government policies and strategies relating to language learning and integration also flags over-reliance on English language and associated anglophone culture despite a growing plurilingual and intercultural population and links such policies to inequality of opportunity in HE.

3.3. Higher Education and Internationalisation

This is an opaque reference to the ascendant phenomenon of transnational education (TNE), which sees Western universities setting up satellite campuses across Asia and the Middle East (Universities UK, 2021). The Hunt Report's reference to the importance of fees paid by non-EU students is thinly veiled. It notes that growing internationalisation will be self-funding and that institutions should set fee levels such that they are competitive but give "due consideration for the enhanced student support that will be provided" (Department of Education and Skills, 2011, p. 85). The report does not stipulate in what, precisely, such supports should ideally consist, and this is reflected in the reality that most institutions offer limited (O'Connor, 2017), piecemeal language support and academic skills training to incoming international learners and that as a result, international students can feel inadequately prepared for their third-level experience (Farrelly and Murphy, 2018).

This ambiguity surrounding the pedagogical innovations and practical supports required meaningfully to scaffold the learning experience of inbound international learners has received significant comment. Farrelly & Murphy (2018) report, for example, that international students in Ireland expressed a wish for better pre-arrival knowledge and information. The identified information gaps, centred around the practical challenges of living in Ireland (such as accommodation), the social (including cultural norms) and the academic (assessment and assessment grading, classroom environment and time/ effort required to stay on top of university work).

4. France

4.1. The Rise of Global English

Salomone (2018) examined the rise of English as a global medium of instruction in higher education, with particular attention to developments in France and Italy. She highlights the growing use of English in university teaching and explores the legal, pedagogical, and sociolinguistic implications of

this development. In France, a significant turning point occurred in 2013, when the Toubon Law – which had previously restricted the use of English as a language of instruction in public universities – was amended. This legislative change allowed the delivery of courses in English under specific conditions, possibly paving the way for a broader commitment to internationalisation within French higher education.

This policy shift coincided with structural reforms such as the Bologna Process, particularly the standardisation of Master's degrees across Europe, which was implemented around 2010. Together, these reforms facilitated a growing emphasis on internationalisation in France, prompting universities to expand English-medium instruction (EMI) as a means of attracting international students and enhancing global competitiveness. However, this trend and subsequent developments have triggered ongoing debates regarding the potential threats that global English poses to national and minority languages, the challenges of maintaining multilingualism, and the risks to the academic integrity of higher education programmes.

One key area of concern involves pedagogy. In the French context, it is frequently noted that students are often inadequately prepared to undertake university-level coursework in English. When both instructors and students have limited fluency, the instructional language may become oversimplified, potentially adversely affecting content delivery. This can negatively impact not only the quality of teaching but also the richness of interaction and dialogue between students and lecturers. Consequently, there is a pressing need to ensure that students acquire an adequate level of English proficiency – ideally, an independent speaking level – prior to entering university programmes taught in English.

Moreover, Salomone raises important questions about equity and access in EMI settings. There is growing concern that English-medium instruction may add to and exacerbate existing social inequalities. Students from more privileged backgrounds often have access to higher-quality language education and are, therefore, better positioned to succeed in EMI programmes. By contrast, students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds may receive less effective language instruction at earlier educational stages, leaving them at a disadvantage when pursuing university-level studies in English. This dynamic risks reinforcing educational and social stratification, whereby access to internationalised academic programmes becomes disproportionately skewed toward elite groups.

In summary, while the expansion of EMI reflects broader goals of internationalisation, it also necessitates careful consideration of language policy, pedagogical quality, and social equity.

Truchot (2018) also examines the public policies of France and Germany in higher education, particularly in relation to the growing process of anglicisation. He argues that while both countries have allowed anglicisation to

develop – largely driven by the pressures of global competitiveness – they have not adequately addressed the associated challenges. The adoption of English is often seen by universities as a strategic necessity for gaining international recognition and remaining competitive in global rankings.

The expansion of Erasmus mobility programmes and the implementation of a unified credit system for Bachelor's and Master's degrees in 2014 further accelerated the internationalisation of higher education, leading to an increase in English-taught courses and institutional policies aimed at attracting international students. In France, this shift has also affected research output. For example, the prestigious Institut Pasteur discontinued its long-running French-language journal *Annales de l'Institut Pasteur* and launched an English-language counterpart, *Research in Microbiology*. This move was emblematic of the broader trend toward English in academic publishing, but it also provoked significant resistance within France, where concerns about the erosion of the French language in academia remain strong.

France's legal framework has played an important role in shaping this dynamic. The Toubon Law of 1994, which aimed to protect the French language, technically allowed the teaching of courses in foreign languages. However, in practice, very few such courses received official accreditation. This changed in 2013, when Higher Education Minister Geneviève Fioraso introduced legislation explicitly designed to facilitate the internationalisation of French university programmes by easing restrictions on English-medium instruction. Additionally, in 2011, the President of the French engineering schools association announced a plan to triple student intake, further reflecting a strong political and economic will to internationalise the sector.

4.2. Public Policies in Higher Education Promoting Anglicisation

Schröder (2018) offers a complementary perspective, critiquing the limitations of the European Commission's motto "Plurilingual European citizens for a multilingual Europe". He contends that this vision has not yielded significant success in practice. Rather than focusing exclusively on traditional, grammar-based instruction, English should be seen as a "gateway language" – a tool to promote broader language awareness, intercultural understanding, and communicative competence. He emphasises the importance of innovative teacher training, new learning formats, and pedagogical strategies that foster cultural and linguistic curiosity, encourage playful learning, and prioritise communicative success over grammatical accuracy. Teachers, he argues, should shift away from error correction toward more holistic approaches to multilingual education.

In France, classrooms are increasingly becoming sites of plurilingual and multicultural interaction. Importantly, the linguistic diversity in these classrooms extends beyond European languages to include global ones, such as

Russian in Germany or Arabic and Portuguese in France. Schröder (2018) argues that European citizens must be equipped to communicate not only regionally, but also globally. To that end, he advocates for educational policies that support the acquisition of multiple languages – even at basic proficiency levels (A2/B1) – rather than a narrow focus on achieving near-native fluency in English. He further recommends that universities implement measures to promote the learning of immigrant and minority languages as part of a genuinely inclusive and global linguistic policy.

5. Conclusions

The comparative review of internationalisation and interculturalism in higher education across Romania, Ireland, and France has uncovered some interesting reoccurring thematic commonalities in each of the separate contexts, revealing both converging trends and distinctive national responses to the globalising pressures on universities. The response to internationalisation in the different countries reflects to a greater or lesser extent varying historical, political, and cultural contexts that influence how internationalisation is understood, implemented, and experienced within their higher education systems.

Internationalisation has clearly become a central policy priority across all three countries driven by economic goals, institutional prestige, and global competitiveness. In Ireland, for example, the process of neoliberal marketisation of the Irish Higher Education sector has put internationalisation on the agenda. Internationalisation is often equated with anglicisation or with teaching more English in HE, as tends to be an emerging policy in France. In Romania, a strong desire for internationalisation is evident across all HEIs at present, with increasingly relevant results on the international academic market. This growing interest reflects not only better developed institutional mechanisms and the presence of a national strategic framework in this regard, but also a heightened awareness among students that the foreign language they are learning – particularly English – will serve as a vital working tool and will be a *sine qua non* requirement in their future profession, ensuring effective and authentic communication.

France's model in the past was notably influenced by state centralism and linguistic protectionism, with internationalisation often situated in tension with national cultural and language policies. In Romania progress has been hampered by the outdated legacy of the Romanian education system. Despite these differences, all countries face the challenge of balancing international ambitions with national traditions and priorities.

Interculturalism, while often positioned in the broader discourse of internationalisation, emerges as a more complex and underdeveloped dimension. The literature indicates that while universities promote diversity and

global citizenship as ideals, the practical integration of intercultural principles into curricula, pedagogy, and student life is uneven, underdeveloped, and under-researched. In Ireland greater attention is given to inclusive teaching practices and support systems for international students, though intercultural engagement is still frequently limited to the formal structures of international offices. Across all contexts, a persistent gap exists between policy-level commitments and the actual fostering of meaningful intercultural dialogue and competence.

Language policy also plays a crucial role in shaping both internationalisation and interculturalism. The increasing dominance of English as the medium of instruction raises concerns about linguistic homogenisation and the marginalisation of local languages.

Overall, the literature underscores that internationalisation and interculturalism should not be viewed merely as measures or metrics of commercialisation or mobility, but as deeply interconnected processes that require critical reflection, inclusive practices, and ongoing engagement. Higher education institutions in Romania, Ireland, and France must move beyond instrumental approaches to embrace internationalisation as a transformative humanising process. This involves fostering environments where cultural diversity is not only present but actively engaged with through curriculum reform, staff development, and student participation.

Future research should further examine how institutional cultures, power dynamics, and student voices shape the intercultural realities of internationalised campuses. Moreover, attention should be paid to how structural inequalities, such as globalising languages, funding disparities, and geopolitical constraints impact the ability of institutions and individuals to engage equitably in international and intercultural education. Only through such an approach can higher education institutions fulfil their vision as significant sites and spaces for intercultural understanding and global citizenship.

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REFERENCES

- Borghetti C., Lertola J., *Interlingual subtitling for intercultural language education: a case study*, *Language and Intercultural Communication*, **14**, 4, 423-440 (2014), <https://doi.org/10.1080/14708477.2014.934380>.
- Brannen M., Piekkari R., Tietze S., *The multifaceted role of language in international business: Unpacking the forms, functions and features of a critical challenge to MNC theory and performance*, *Journal of International Business Studies*, **45**, 495-507 (2014), <https://doi.org/10.1057/jibs.2014.24>.

- Bruen J., Kelly N., *Language teaching in a globalised world: harnessing linguistic super-diversity in the classroom*, *International Journal of Multilingualism*, **13**, 3, 333-352 (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790718.2016.1142548>.
- Bruen J., Sudhershana A., "So, They're Actually Real?" *Integrating E-Tandem Learning into the Study of Language for International Business*, *Journal of Teaching in International Business*, **26**, 2, 81-93 (2015).
- Deca L., Egron-Polak E., Fiț C.R., *Internationalisation of Higher Education in Romanian National and Institutional Contexts*, in Curaj A., Deca L., Egron-Polak E., Salmi, J. (Eds.), *Higher Education Reforms in Romania*, Springer, Cham, pp. 127-147, 2015, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-08054-3_7.
- Department of Education and Skills, *National Strategy for Higher Education to 2030*, Department of Education and Skills, Dublin, 2011.
- Dima V., Mohanu F., Pătru C., Rusu O.C., Șerban-Oprescu A-T., *Multilingualism and Internationalization of Higher Education*, *SYNERGY*, **19**, 2, 109-126 (2023), <http://dx.doi.org/10.24818/SYN/2023/19/2.01>.
- Farrelly T., Murphy T., *Hindsight is 20/20 vision: What international students wished they had known before coming to live and learn in Ireland*, *Journal of International Students*, **8**, 4, 1848-1864 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.32674/jis.v8i4.234>.
- Fiț C.-R., Panțir C.A., Cheregi B.-F., *Romanian Universities: The Use of Educational Marketing to Strengthen Internationalization of Higher Education*, in Curaj A., Salmi J., Hâj C.M. (Eds.), *Higher Education in Romania: Overcoming Challenges and Embracing Opportunities*, Springer, Cham, pp. 169-191, 2022, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-94496-4_9.
- Gheorghiu C.M., *Intercultural education – Analysis and Perspectives*, *Florya Chronicles of Political Economy*, **3**, 2, 71-104 (2017).
- Grosu-Rădulescu L.-M., *Constructing and Construing the Place of Romanian Foreign Language Education in the European Context*, in Grosu-Rădulescu L.-M. (Ed.), *Foreign Language Teaching in Romanian Higher Education: Teaching Methods, Learning Outcomes*, Springer, Cham, pp. 3-15, 2018, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-93329-0_1.
- Hamburg A., *The Role of Foreign Language Teachers in Developing Students' Intercultural Communication Skills*, *Journal of Languages for Specific Purposes*, **1**, 1, Oradea, 78-85 (2014).
- Jeanneau C., O'Riordan S., *Peer-led discussion groups in foreign languages: Training international students to become peer-facilitators*, *Studies in Self-Access Learning Journal*, **6**, 4, 433-443 (2015).
- Loxley A., *From Seaweed & Peat to Pills & Very Small Things: Knowledge Production and Higher Education in the Irish Context*, in Loxley A., Seery A., Walsh J. (Eds.), *Higher Education in Ireland*, Palgrave Macmillan, London, pp. 55-85, 2014, https://doi.org/10.1057/9781137289889_4.
- Ni Chonail B., *Interculturalism in Higher Education in Ireland. An analysis from a Strategy, Policy and Practice Perspective*, *Studies in Health Technology and Informatics*, **256**, 624-633 (2018), <https://doi.org/10.3233/978-1-61499-923-2-624>.

- Nunan A., *Giving learners a multicultural voice: An English-speaking university context*, *Language Learning in Higher Education*, **7**, 2, 435-449 (2017), <http://dx.doi.org/10.1515/cercles-2017-0018>.
- O'Connor S., *Problematising strategic internationalisation: tensions and conflicts between international student recruitment and integration policy in Ireland*, *Globalisation, Societies and Education*, **16**, 3, 339-352 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1080/14767724.2017.1413979>.
- Pauwels T., *Populism in Western Europe. Comparing Belgium, Germany and The Netherlands*, Routledge, Abingdon, 2014.
- Salomone R., *The Rise of Global English: Challenges for English-medium Instruction and language*, in Le Lièvre F., Anquetil M., Derivry-Plard M., Fäcke Ch., Verstraete-Hansen L. (Eds.), *Langues et cultures dans l'internationalisation de l'enseignement supérieur au XXIe siècle. (Re)penser les politiques linguistiques : anglais et plurilinguisme*, Peter Lang, Bern/Berlin, pp. 59-90, 2018.
- Schröder K., *Trying to reconcile European Language Politics and Linguistic Realities in a World of Globalisation: A call for Innovation, European Educational Policies, Foreign Language Teaching and Teaching Methods*, in Le Lièvre F., Anquetil M., Derivry-Plard M., Fäcke Ch., Verstraete-Hansen L. (Eds.), *Langues et cultures dans l'internationalisation de l'enseignement supérieur au XXIe siècle. (Re)penser les politiques linguistiques : anglais et plurilinguisme*, Peter Lang, Bern/Berlin, pp. 163-177, 2018.
- Truchot C., *Internationalisation, anglicisation et politiques publiques de l'enseignement supérieur*, in Le Lièvre F., Anquetil M., Derivry-Plard M., Fäcke Ch., Verstraete-Hansen L. (Eds.), *Langues et cultures dans l'internationalisation de l'enseignement supérieur au XXIe siècle. (Re)penser les politiques linguistiques : anglais et plurilinguisme*, Peter Lang, Bern/Berlin, pp. 41-57, 2018.
- Universities UK, 2021. *What is UK higher education transnational education?* [Online] Available at: <https://www.universitiesuk.ac.uk/universities-uk-international/explore-uuki/transnational-education/what-uk-higher-education-transnational> [Accessed 20 November 2021].

INTERNAȚIONALIZARE ȘI INTERCULTURALISM ÎN TREI CONTEXTE
EUROPENE: O SCURTĂ TRECERE ÎN REVISTĂ A LITERATURII DE
SPECIALITATE

(Rezumat)

Articolul explorează literatura de specialitate privind internaționalizarea și interculturalismul în învățământul superior din Irlanda, România și Franța. Sunt identificate teme comune și diferențe naționale, modelate de factori politici, istorici și lingvistici. Internaționalizarea reprezintă o politică majoră în toate cele trei țări, fiind adesea asociată cu priorități economice și instituționale, iar limba engleză este tot mai frecvent utilizată ca limbă de predare. Cu toate acestea, competențele interculturale

rămân slab dezvoltate, cu o integrare limitată în planurile de învățământ și în viața studenților, creând astfel un decalaj între angajamentele asumate la nivel de politici și practicile interculturale reale. Deși strategiile naționale diferă, toate cele trei contexte se confruntă cu provocări comune în asigurarea unui echilibru între aspirațiile globale și identitățile locale și prin urmare, există argumente pentru adoptarea unor abordări mai incluzive și mai reflexive ale internaționalizării, dincolo de cele pur instrumentale. Cercetările viitoare ar trebui să se axeze pe modul în care cultura instituțională, dinamica puterii și politicile lingvistice influențează experiențele studenților și educația interculturală globală.